

DIFFERENTIAL TENGLAMAGA QO‘YILGAN KOSHI MASALASINING ANIQ VA TAQRIBIY YECHIMLARINI MathCad TIZIMIDA TAQQOSLASH

Allamuratov Sharapatdin Ziuatdinovich

Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari universiteti Nukus filiali

Fizika matematika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Djoldasbaeva Aqsuliy Bagitovna

Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari universiteti Nukus filiali

assistent o‘qituvchisi

Ziuatdinov Islambek Sharapatdinovich

Sankt-Peterburg informatsia texnologiyalari mexanika va optika universiteti

magistranti

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada differentsial tenglamalarga qo‘yilgan koshi masalasining aniq va taqribiy yechimlarini topish usuli keltirilgan va misol tariqasida differentsial tenglama matcad tizimida taqqoslangan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Koshi masalasi, iteratsiya, Pikar usuli.

Faraz qilaylik, bizga quyidagi Koshi masalasi berilgan bo‘lsin [1].

$$y' = f(x, y), \quad (1)$$

$$y(x_0) = y_0. \quad (2)$$

Bu masalani echish uchun differentsial tenglamalar kursidan ma`lum bo‘lgan ketma-ket yaqinlashish usulini

$$y_n(x) = y_0 + \int_{x_0}^x f(t, y_{n-1}(t)) dt \quad (3)$$

$$y_0(t) \equiv y_0, \quad n = 1, 2, \dots$$

qo‘llab yoki yechimni x_0 nuqta atrofida qatorga (odatda Teylor qatoriga) yoyish usulini qo‘llab, yechimni taqribiy analitik ko‘rinishini topishadi

$$y(x) \approx y_n(x) = \sum_{i=0}^n y^{(i)}(x_0) \frac{(x - x_0)^i}{i!}. \quad (4)$$

Bu ikkala sodda usullar ma`lum kamchiliklarga ega, xususan birinchisida har bir yangi yaqinlashishda integral hisoblanishi lozim bo‘lsa, ikkinchisida esa $|x - x_0|$ kichik bo‘lmasa (4) qator yaqinlashmasligi mumkin yoki juda sust yaqinlashuvchi bo‘ladi. Shu bois ham (1) - (2) masalani boshqa usullar bilan yechishni o‘rganamiz.

Mayli quyidagi differentsial tenglama

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = f(x, u, t), \quad x \in R^n, \quad u \in R^m, \quad t \in [0, t], \quad (5)$$

$$x(0) = x^0$$

boshlang‘ich shartta berilgan bo‘lsin. Koshi masalasi echimining bor bo‘lishi haqidagi teorema quydagi iteratsion jarayonning yaqinlashuvchiligiga asoslangan, u (5) tenglamani integrallash asosida olingan.

$$x(t)_{k+1} = x(0) + \int_0^t f(x(\tau)_k, u(\tau)) d\tau, \quad x(0) = x^0, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots \quad (6)$$

Bu jarayon yuqoridagi shartlarda yaqinlashuvchi bwladi va oddiy differentsial tenglamani integrallash usuli Pikar usuli dep ataladi [2,3].

Quydagi chiziqli tenglamaga qoyilgan Koshi masalasini aniq va taqribiy yechamiz.

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dx}{dt} = t^2 - x^2, \\ x(0) = 0. \end{cases}$$

Echimi: Tenglamaning aniq yechimi erikli doimiyni variyatsiyalash yoki Lagranj usulidan foydalanib yechiladi. Uning uchun dastlab $\frac{dx}{dt} + x^2 = 0$, birjinsli tenglama yechimi topiladi. Birjinsli tenglama yechimi $x = c(t)e^{-\int p(t)dt}$, ko‘rinishda qidiriladi, bunda s(t) –topish kerak bwlgan t-ning uzluksiz funksiyasi va $p(t) = 1, \quad q(t) = t^2$.

Umumiy yechim $x = e^{-\int p(t)dt} \left(C + \int q(t)e^{\int p(t)dt} dt \right)$, formulasidan foydalansak

$$x = e^{-t} \left(C + \int t^2 e^t dt \right) = \left| \begin{array}{ll} u = t^2 & du = 2t dt \\ dv = e^t dt & v = e^t \end{array} \right| =$$

$$= e^{-t} \left(C + t^2 e^t - 2 \int t e^t dt \right) = \left| \begin{array}{ll} u = t & du = dt \\ dv = e^t dt & v = e^t \end{array} \right| =$$

$$= e^{-t} \left(C + t^2 e^t - 2t e^t + 2e^t \right) = C e^{-t} + t^2 - 2t + 2,$$

$$x(0) = 0; \quad 0 = C + 2 \Rightarrow C = -2.$$

Aniq yechim $x = -2e^{-t} + t^2 - 2t + 2$, ko‘rinishida bo‘ladi.

MathCad tizimidagi dasturi quydagicha. Bu yerda aniq yechim bilan taqribiy yechimlar taqqoslangan [4].

$$x_n := 0 \quad f(x, t) := t^2 - x^2 \quad x_0 := 0$$

$$x_1(t) := x_n + \int_0^t f(x_0, \tau) d\tau \rightarrow \frac{1}{3} \cdot t^3$$

$$x_2(t) := x_n + \int_0^t f(x_1(t), \tau) d\tau \rightarrow \frac{1}{3} \cdot t^3 - \frac{1}{9} \cdot t^7$$

$$x_3(t) := x_n + \int_0^t f(x_2(t), \tau) d\tau \rightarrow \frac{1}{3} \cdot t^3 - \frac{1}{9} \cdot t^7 + \frac{2}{27} \cdot t^{11} - \frac{1}{81} \cdot t^{15}$$

$$x_4(t) := x_n + \int_0^t f(x_3(t), \tau) d\tau \rightarrow \frac{1}{3} \cdot t^3 - \frac{1}{9} \cdot t^7 + \frac{2}{27} \cdot t^{11} - \frac{5}{81} \cdot t^{15} + \frac{2}{81} \cdot t^{19} - \frac{2}{243} \cdot t^{23} + \frac{4}{2187} \cdot t^{27} - \frac{1}{6561} \cdot t^3$$

$$t := 0, 0.05..1$$

$x_4(t) =$

0
4.167·10 ⁻⁵
3.333·10 ⁻⁴
1.125·10 ⁻³
2.665·10 ⁻³
5.202·10 ⁻³
8.976·10 ⁻³
0.014
0.021
0.03
0.041
0.054
0.069
0.087
0.106
0.128

$x_3(t) =$

0
4.167·10 ⁻⁵
3.333·10 ⁻⁴
1.125·10 ⁻³
2.665·10 ⁻³
5.202·10 ⁻³
8.976·10 ⁻³
0.014
0.021
0.03
0.041
0.054
0.069
0.087
0.107
0.129

$-2e^{-t} + t^2 - 2t + 2 =$

0
4.115·10 ⁻⁵
3.252·10 ⁻⁴
1.084·10 ⁻³
2.538·10 ⁻³
4.898·10 ⁻³
8.364·10 ⁻³
0.013
0.019
0.027
0.037
0.049
0.062
0.078
0.097
0.118

Bunda $x_3(t)$, $x_4(t)$ taqribiy yechimlar, aniq yechim $x = -2e^{-t} + t^2 - 2t + 2$,

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlat:

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